

Spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) using some arylazo-bis-acetoximes

Gena Ram, R. S. Chauhan, A. K. Goswami*^a and D. N. Purohit^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001, India

^bM. D. S. University, Ajmer-305 001, India

Manuscript received 21 October 2002, accepted 11 May 2004

A spectrophotometric method has been described for determination of cobalt(II) using *p*-bromophenylazo-bis-acetoxime and *o*-methoxyphenylazo-bis-acetoxime. The reagents form yellow complexes in the pH range 7.5 to 8.5 and absorb at 376 and 380 nm, respectively. Stability constants and free energy have been calculated. The Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range $0.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $1.4 \times 10^{-4} M$ of cobalt(II). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are $3947 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 14.93 ng cm^{-2} and $3079 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 19.14 ng cm^{-2} , respectively. The interference of various ions has been studied.

Arylazo-bis-acetoximes are similar to hydroxytriazenes. Although a number of spectrophotometric studies for cobalt(II) determination using hydroxytriazenes as reagents have been done¹, no studies have appeared by the use of arylazo-bis-acetoximes. Thus in the present investigation in continuation of our earlier studies two new arylazo-bis-acetoximes have been used to determine Co^{II} spectrophotometrically.

Results and discussion

On the basis of composition studies it is revealed that cobalt(II) forms 1 : 2 complexes $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{L}]$ with *p*-bromophenylazo-bis-acetoxime [*p*-BPABA] and *o*-methoxyphenylazo-bis-acetoxime [*o*-MPABA]. These ligands are mono basic bidentate ligand and are expected to form square planar complexes with Co^{II} . The probable structure, which may be assigned to these complexes, may be represented as

where

$R_1 = \text{Br}, \text{OCH}_3$

The stability constants have been determined by Harvey and Manning's method² using mole ratio curves and Purohit's method³ using Job's curves. The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The $\log \beta$ values obtained from both the methods agree well indicating the validity of the method. Further, precision studies considering ten values of absorbance gave precision of 5.89 ± 0.028 and 5.89 ± 0.033 ppm of cobalt(II), respectively.

The above studies thus conclude that the reagents can be successfully applied for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II). Easy synthesis of the reagents using inexpensive chemicals further enhances the utility of the reagents.

Experimental

Synthesis of reagents : Method for preparing hydroxytriazenes and analogous compounds arylazo-bis-acetoximes have been reported in the literature⁴. Arylazo-bis-acetoximes were prepared by the reported method⁵. The brief details are given in following paragraphs.

***p*-Bromophenylazo-bis-acetoxime :** *p*-Bromoaniline (17.2 g) was diazotized at below 5° . Further, diazotized product was coupled at 0° under mechanical stirring with freshly prepared solution of acetoxime (12 g) in 150 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide. Light pink coloured granular precipitate separated out which was filtered under suction and washed with petroleum ether ($40-60^\circ$). Crude product was treated with activated charcoal. The final compound was obtained as yellow needle shaped crystals having m.p. 144° .

***o*-Methoxyphenylazo-bis-acetoxime :** *o*-Anisidine (11.3 g) was diazotized below 5° . Further, diazotized product was coupled with solution of acetoxime (12 g) as same proce-

Table 1. The values of log β and ΔG by Harvey and Manning's method

Name of the reagent	Composition of complex [Co ^{II} : R]	Conc. of complex	E_m	E_s	α	K_{inst}	β	log β	ΔG at 25° kcal mol ⁻¹
<i>p</i> -Bromophenylazo-bis-acetoxime	1 : 2	5×10^{-5}	0.255	0.172	0.323	5.08×10^{-10}	1.97×10^9	9.29	-12.67
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylazo-bis-acetoxime	1 : 2	5×10^{-5}	0.186	0.134	0.279	3.01×10^{-10}	3.32×10^9	9.52	-12.98

Table 2. The values of log β and ΔG by Purohit's method

Name of the reagent	Composition of complex [Co ^{II} : R]	Conc. of complex	E_m	E_s	α	K_{inst}	β	log β	ΔG at 25° kcal mol ⁻¹
<i>p</i> -Bromophenylazo-bis-acetoximes	1 : 2	2×10^{-4}	0.800	0.675	0.156	7.19×10^{-10}	1.39×10^9	9.14	-12.46
		1×10^{-4}	0.425	0.336	0.209	4.62×10^{-10}	2.16×10^9	9.33	-12.72
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylazo-bis-acetoximes	1 : 2	2×10^{-4}	0.605	0.528	0.127	3.75×10^{-10}	2.67×10^9	9.43	-12.46
		1×10^{-5}	0.325	0.264	0.188	3.27×10^{-10}	3.06×10^9	9.52	-12.92

ture as described above. Crude product was treated with activated charcoal. It was then crystallized twice from alcohol. The final compound was obtained as cream coloured micro crystals having m.p. 98°.

A stock solution of cobalt(II) ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared by dissolving appropriate quantity of A.R. grade cobalt nitrate hexahydrate (B.D.H.) in double-distilled water and a few drops of concentrated nitric acid were added to prevent hydrolysis. Stock solution of reagents ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) were prepared in alcohol and dilute solutions were prepared using this stock solution. Tris-buffer solution was prepared by dissolving tris-(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (1.0 g) in minimum quantity of water and then made upto 100 ml with ethanol.

Spectra were taken on UV-Vis Systronics spectrophotometer-108 and pH was measured on a Systronics pH meter-324.

Interference studies : The effect of several interfering cations and anions on the absorbance of cobalt complex was also studied at 10, 50 and 100 ppm level of interfering ions. The anions and cations, which did not interfere at 10 ppm level were screened at 50 and 100 ppm level. The cations used for the interference studies were : Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, V⁴⁺. Anions used for the study of interference were : CH₃COO⁻, NO₂⁻, CO₃²⁻, SO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, F⁻, I⁻.

Following were the observation for interference by various ions in case of *p*-BPABA and *o*-MPABA for the determination of 5.89 ppm of cobalt(II). For *p*-PBABA, it was observed that Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, F⁻ did not interfere even upto 100 ppm, Pb²⁺, Ba²⁺ did not interfere at 50 ppm and Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Hg²⁺, V⁴⁺, CH₃COO⁻, NO₂⁻, CO₃²⁻ did not interfere at 10 ppm level. For *o*-MPABA, it was observed that K⁺, Na⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, F⁻ did not interfere even upto 100 ppm, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, NO₂⁻, SO₄²⁻, CO₃²⁻ did not interfere at 50 ppm and SO₃²⁻, CH₃COO⁻, Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺ did not interfere at 10 ppm level.

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